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MANAGEMENT OF INTEGRATED MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article provides information about manufacturing enterprises, production processes, the role of production in the country's economy, the organization of production, and production. It also provides ideas about the factors affecting the organization of the production process in Uzbekistan.

Key words: production, manufacturing enterprises, production process, organization of the production process.

INTRODUCTION

In the economies of countries around the world, great attention is being paid to the organization of integrated production systems and the improvement of their management mechanisms. These processes, through the use of modern innovative management strategies, allow increasing the competitiveness of manufacturing enterprises and effectively organizing all stages of production from raw materials to finished products. Scientific research in this regard, in particular, improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of production, is of great importance. Practical experience of countries around the world shows that economic integration is one of the main factors in increasing production efficiency, strengthening competitiveness and improving the well-being of the population.

Also, research on the integration of manufacturing enterprises in different countries is focused on issues related to the property rights of large manufacturers, optimal use of production resources, and the quality of products and services. In particular, great attention is being paid to the development of the textile industry. Scientific research is being carried out on the effective management of production in textile clusters, increasing product exports and reducing imports. These studies will allow to increase the competitiveness of the textile industry, increase exports and develop effective mechanisms for the production of import-substituting products.

Among the main tasks set by the Uzbekistan Strategy "Uzbekistan-2030" are the development of important sectors of the industry, including the textile industry, full utilization of production potential and expansion of exports[1]. In implementing these strategic goals, it is important to localize products, simplify and diversify exports, strengthen cooperation between economic sectors, and create new high-income jobs. At the same time, it is planned to expand Uzbekistan's export potential, implement large-scale projects in the textile industry to produce high-quality yarn and fabrics, and introduce modern technologies.

In the future, it is planned to create new opportunities in the world market by developing integrated production systems and increasing their competitiveness in our country, accelerating economic integration processes, and expanding the country's foreign economic activity. This, in turn, will allow Uzbekistan to take its place in the global division of labor.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Among modern scientists engaged in the integration of production forms at enterprises, it is worth mentioning D.P. Barsukov[2], D.M. Begov,[3] V.I. Vagizova[4], V.V. Ilin[5], Yu.A. Achenbach[6], N.N. Shutko[7], G.D. Boush[8], L.L. Butuzova[9], R.R. Tokhchukov, E.V. Chemodanov, A. Fridman, A.A. Migranyan, T.V. Uskova, E.V. Volkodavova, T.I. Maksimova, L.I. Pronyaeva, O.A. Fedotenkova, A.V. Pavlova, V.V. Pechatkin, M.A. Nikolaev and others.

In our opinion, despite the existence of several scientific studies by domestic and foreign economists, there is a need for a comprehensive and thorough analysis of issues related to the management of enterprises focused on the production of integrated products. It is important to further deepen research in this area and identify problems, as well as develop new methods that will help effectively manage business and production strategies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the theories and opinions put forward by domestic and foreign scientists on the management of enterprises aimed at the production of integrated products were separately studied and fully analyzed. Also, the main goal of the study was to improve the management mechanisms of business structures aimed at the production of integrated products, which play an important role in the economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. To achieve this goal, various factors affecting the management mechanisms of the enterprise were intensively analyzed theoretically and practically, and new models were developed based on the identified factors aimed at improving the management process and system. The study effectively used inductive and deductive methods, systematic and logical analysis, as well as economic analysis methods, which helped to make the analysis and conclusions of the work clear and reliable.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Economic integration is the process of interconnection, cooperation, and integration between enterprises, sectors, regions, countries, and states, which is carried out with the aim of ensuring economic development, efficient allocation of resources, and the elimination of barriers between markets. This integration helps to create new opportunities in various sectors and markets, ensure economic stability, and increase global competitiveness.

Economic integration is an objective process, which is associated with a number of important factors. The first of the main reasons for this process is the further deepening of the international division of labor, which expands the opportunities for each state to use its own expertise and resources. Secondly, the free movement of capital internationally and the disappearance of investment borders accelerate the integration process. The third factor is global development in the field of science and technology, which leads to the widespread dissemination of new innovations and technologies on a global scale. Fourth, openness and export orientation in the process of growth of national economies contribute to the further strengthening of economic cooperation between countries. Together, these factors ensure the development and effectiveness of economic integration (figure 1).

Figure 1. Integration factors for national development.

International division of labor	is the distribution of labor and resources between different countries. In this system, each country specializes in certain areas, depending on its economic and social capabilities, skilled labor force, and technological development. As a result, there is an exchange of products and services between countries, which leads to the effective development of the global economy. The international division of labor not only optimizes production processes, but also strengthens economic ties between countries and helps to increase the well-being of different peoples.
internationalization of capital	The international movement of capital contributes to the efficient allocation of economic resources, the opening of new markets, and the development of production in many countries. In this process, transnational corporations and international investors also invest in local markets, bringing in technologies and unique knowledge, which in turn contributes to the modernization and competitiveness of countries' economies.
scientific and technical technological development	This is the process of creating, developing and implementing new achievements in science and technology. This development includes modern scientific research, the creation of new technologies, the development of innovative methods and advanced devices. These processes serve to make people's lives more comfortable, ensure economic growth and protect the environment. At the same time, scientific and technological progress increases the competitiveness of countries, creates new markets on a global scale and plays an important role in solving global problems.

openness of national economies in growth

It refers to the integration of countries into the global economy and economic activity that includes factors such as foreign investment, trade, technology, and knowledge exchange. Openness helps to diversify the economy, open up new markets, and make national production more efficient. In other words, countries' economies grow by using foreign resources, products, and technologies, which allows them to create new jobs, innovate, and ensure economic stability. The openness of the national economy also allows countries to increase their competitiveness, expand their export opportunities, and develop cooperation with other countries. In this way, openness not only accelerates economic growth, but also serves to strengthen the national economy through international trade and investment.

Large integrated enterprises often play an important role in the clustering process. By an integrated enterprise, we mean a set of business entities that carry out several types of activities and increase efficiency by coordinating these processes with each other and creating added value. Such enterprises are engaged in the production, processing and distribution of goods and services, and their activities are based on centralized management. Integrated enterprises, as a rule, combine interconnected industries and optimize economic processes. The most common and effective integration model is clustering, that is, enterprises operating in the same or similar industries work together, which increases their competitiveness and overall efficiency. Clusters are also important in developing innovations, opening new markets and reducing production costs.

The main features that characterize the sustainable development of a cluster include such factors as strong cooperation between organizations and enterprises within the cluster, effective allocation of resources, innovative activity and rapid adaptation to market needs. In other words, the sustainable development of a cluster depends on ensuring interdependence, mutual assistance and competitiveness between its members. Within a cluster, enterprises exchange their knowledge and technologies, work together to create new products and improve production processes. Also, long-term relations and economic cooperation between cluster members are of great importance for sustainable development. At the same time, the ability of a cluster to constantly update its activities, taking into account market requirements, social and environmental factors, is also a key factor in ensuring its sustainability. The successful development of clusters is also closely related to the availability of social infrastructure and a favorable legal and regulatory environment.

In order to ensure the rapid development of manufacturing enterprises and downstream processing enterprises, it is very important to use the most modern and efficient technologies in the period under review. With the help of such technologies, enterprises will be able to optimize production processes, increase resource efficiency and improve product quality. Modern technologies also play an important role in creating new products, quickly and effectively responding to market demands, and reducing production costs. In particular, it is necessary to introduce technological innovations and news to increase competitiveness and successfully operate in global markets. Also, the use of advanced technologies in processing enterprises will help to make production processes more efficient, reduce waste, and protect the environment. Thus, the introduction of the best technologies in the period under review will not only ensure the economic growth of enterprises, but also strengthen their future success.

It is important to ensure social protection for employees of cluster enterprises, to ensure that their working conditions and well-being are not lower than the average in other enterprises. Such social protection will help employees not only in labor rights, but also in areas such as health care, pension provision, education and training. Through cooperation and exchange of resources between cluster members, a higher level of social guarantees for employees is created. This process also contributes to the establishment of a fair and balanced system of labor relations, the effective work of employees and their personal well-being. By providing stable and socially responsible working conditions for its employees, each enterprise in the cluster creates a social environment necessary for their motivation, increased competitiveness and long-term development.

Establishing an optimized balance between consumed and created resources means ensuring the efficient use of resources in economic activity and harmonizing production and consumption processes. Creating such a balance is based, on the one hand, on the correct distribution of resources created in the production process and their delivery to users, and on the other hand, on the provision of quality products and services that meet the requirements of consumers. Resources should be used as efficiently as possible in production, without wasting them and without harming the environment. In this case, maintaining a balance between production processes and consumption needs helps to ensure economic stability and social well-being in the long term. At the same time, this process should be carried out taking into account resource recycling, energy efficiency and environmental safety. Thus, an optimized balance between consumption and production resources serves to ensure economically and environmentally sustainable development.

Within the framework of a territorial association, fulfilling all obligations to external stakeholders means ensuring mutual agreements and cooperation between members within the association, as well as the full and timely implementation of obligations set forth in relation to external parties, that is, states, international organizations or other business entities. It is necessary to develop cooperation between the states or organizations that make up the territorial association, based on the unification of their economic, political and social interests. At the same time, compliance by all members of the association with agreements, contracts and agreements concluded with external parties serves to establish stable economic relations at the regional and global levels. Fulfilling these obligations, in turn, stimulates regional development, promotes the development of trade and investment, and strengthens international relations. Also, territorial associations achieve success in fulfilling obligations to external stakeholders on the basis of mutual respect, trust and cooperation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Currently, the issues of expanding new segments in the world market and gaining dominance in them by increasing the competitiveness of products of promising integrated manufacturing enterprises in our country are very important and urgent. Through this, the goals of developing the country's foreign economic activity, integrating into the global division of labor and finding a place for itself should be realized. The sustainable development strategy, which is implemented through increasing competitiveness in the world market, modernization and renewal of the country's economy, and the use of innovative technologies, is of great importance in this regard. Technological innovations and highly effective innovations help ensure integration into the world community, which ensures the country's active participation in global economic processes.

The use of various forms and methods of integration mechanisms of manufacturing enterprises of the economy creates opportunities not only to create effective means of protection against the negative effects of the external environment, but also to develop effective self-regulating structures. The expediency of this process plays an important role in maintaining the stability of the economic system and clearly defining its future development directions. Working on integration and innovative development will help increase the efficiency of the economy and ensure the competitiveness of our country in the global market.

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